

Mapping Micronutrients status in KRP Dam Catchment of Tamil Nadu

A Diagnostic Kit to Paddy Farmers

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Soil plays a significant role in determining the sustainable productivity of an agro ecosystem. It is one of the essential sources of micronutrients for plants. Out of the 16 essential nutrients, Zinc (Zn), Copper (Cu), Iodine (I), Manganese (Mn), Molybdenum (Mo), Boron (B) and Iron (Fe) are referred micronutrients. These micronutrients are required in small quantities but have agronomic importance as they play a vital role in the growth and development of plants (Ye *et al.*, 2015). Crop yield will be affected if any of these elements are lacking or excessive in the soil with other nutrients. Micronutrient deficiencies are alarmingly increased across the globe and further aggravated by many new cultivars as they are highly sensitive to micronutrient deficiency. Soils widely vary in micronutrient content and supply ability for optimal crop growth. Soil's total micronutrient content is determined by the original geologic substrate and subsequent geochemical and pedogenic regimes. However, the total content is rarely indicative of available micronutrients as they depend on soil pH, organic matter content, surface area, and other physical, chemical, and biological conditions in the rhizosphere (Srinivasan *et al.*, 2021).

Plant uptake or techniques that correlate quantities of micronutrients extracted from soils are used to measure the availability of plants. Rational micronutrient management requires understanding how total and plant-available soil micronutrients vary across the soils. Various approaches have been used to map the status and distribution of soil micronutrients and availability at scales ranging from global to individual farmer's fields. Soil micronutrient mapping for larger areas will guide us to understand the nature and extent of micronutrient problems (Shukla *et al.*, 2015).

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Detailed micronutrient maps (at 1:10000 scale) in individual fields are being developed for site-specific micronutrient management in precision agriculture. Modern tools like the Global positioning system (GPS), and geographic information systems (GIS), integrated with remote sensing technology, help policymakers with proper and balanced micronutrient management for sustainable crop production.

The Krishnagiri reservoir (KRP) is contributed by the river south Pennar, located about 6 km southwest of the Krishnagiri town of Tamil Nadu. The total command area is around 12482 ha, with paddy as a major crop. These paddy-growing soils are deficient in multi-nutrients with poor drainage capacity and soil sodicity /alkalinity due to high-water tables (Srinivasan *et al.*, 2019). This necessitates the identification of micronutrient deficiency in dam catchment, especially in paddy soils, which helps correct the specific nutrient deficiency and sustainable crop production.

Status and distribution micronutrients KRP Dam Catchment

Soil samples were collected from KRP dam catchment area and analyzed for the micronutrient status. After analysis it was categorized as deficient and sufficient in the specific micronutrient. The results are presented below

Table. 1 Area wise distribution of different micronutrients in Dam catchment

Nutrients	Class	Area (ha)	% TGA
Iron (Fe)	Deficient (< 4.5 ppm)	2507	20.08
	Sufficient (> 4.5 ppm)	7556	60.53
Manganese (Mn)	Deficient (< 3.0 ppm)	5728	45.89
	Sufficient (> 3.0 ppm)	4335	34.73
Copper (Cu)	Deficient (< 0.2 ppm)	-	-
	Sufficient (> 0.2 ppm)	10064	80.62

Zinc (Zn)	Deficient (< 0.8 ppm)	6190	49.58
	Sufficient (> 0.8 ppm)	3874	31.03
Boron (B)	Low (< 0.5 ppm)	7603	60.90
	Medium (0.5-1.0 ppm)	2460	19.70

1. Iron (Fe)

Iron (Fe) is an essential micronutrient for crop growth and food production. It is the component of many enzymes associated with energy transfer, nitrogen reduction and fixation, and lignin formation. Fe is required for electron transport during photosynthesis. Plants uptake Fe in ferrous (Fe^{2+}) form. It is one of the most notable elements in paddy soils as it is abundant and undergoes redox

transformation (Kyuma, 2004). Solubility of Fe increases after flooding and during organic matter decomposition (Dobermann and Fairhurst, 2000). Fe deficiency occurs when the soil concentration is below 4-5 ppm in rice soils while toxicity occurs above 300 ppm. In KRP Dam catchment, 2507 ha (20.08%) area is deficient in Fe. The deficiency zones were mapped with GIS that helps the farmers to know the status of Fe in their region.

2. Manganese (Mn)

Manganese (Mn) is a primary part of enzyme systems in plants and is involved in activating essential metabolic reactions and plays a direct role in photosynthesis. It also involved in oxidation-reduction reactions in the electron transport system and oxygen evolution in photosynthesis. Mn accelerates the germination of paddy seedlings while

increasing the availability of phosphorus (P) and calcium (Ca). In KRP dam catchment, 5728 ha (45.89%) area is under Mn deficiency. Identification of critical Mn deficient soils helps to improve the paddy productivity in KRP dam Catchment.

3. Copper (Cu)

Cu is required for lignin synthesis and is a constituent of ascorbic acid and enzymes. It is a regulatory factor in enzyme reactions and a catalyst in oxidation reactions. In soils, Cu present as oxides, carbonates, silicates and sulphides and its chemistry in submerged soils is similar to that of Zn, forming sparingly soluble sulphides. Cu generally accumulated in the upper few centimetres of soils; however, it tends to be adsorbed by soil organic matter, carbonates, clay minerals and oxyhydroxides of Mn and Fe and accumulated in deeper layers of soil (Kabata Pendias, 2011). Cu concentration is sufficient in the study area as they are above critical levels of 0.2 ppm for rice production.

4. Zinc (Zn)

Plants take up zinc (Zn) as the divalent Zn^{+2} cation. Zn was the first micronutrients recognized as essential for plants and most commonly limiting yields. Though Zn requirement is meager, high yields are impossible if it is deficient. It is reportedly deficient in many paddy growing areas in the dam catchment. Available Zn status in the majority of the paddy growing soils (<0.8 ppm) was deficient. A sufficient (>0.8 ppm)

level of Zn was recorded in 31.03% of the KRP Dam catchment (Table 1). The extent and distribution of available Zn shown as thematic maps.

5. Boron (B)

Boron (B) is a unique non-metal micronutrient required for plants' normal growth and

development. It is mobile in soils and more often gets leached down the soil profile with excess moisture. B deficiency and toxicity range are very narrow. Boron concentration and its bioavailability in soils are affected by parent material, texture, clay minerals, pH, liming, organic matter content, sources of irrigation, interrelationship with other elements, and environmental conditions like rainfall and temperature. Boron (B) exists in soil as the BO_3^{-3} anion common plant uptake form. One of the most important micronutrients affecting membrane stability, B supports the structural and functional integrity of plant cell membranes. Boron-deficiency symptoms first appear at the growing points, and certain soil types are more prone to boron deficiencies.

Conclusion

Plants differ in their requirements for specific micronutrients. More than 40 % area was deficient in Mn, Zn, and B, whereas 20% area was deficient in Fe and Cu in the KRP dam catchment. These results showed that the paddy soils in KRP Dam Catchment are highly heterogeneous in micronutrient content. Identification of micronutrients deficient zones and mapping in GIS environment is a useful tool for better site-specific micronutrient management. Proper attention should be paid to the deficient nutrient through appropriate nutrient management practices for increasing the soil nutrient availability and sustain the yield and quality of paddy crop in

the KRP Dam catchment.

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